

Studies on Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Chromium(III) with Thiodisuccinic Acid

S. K. TIWARI, D. P. S. RATHORE and R. PRAKASH

Chemical Laboratories, Z. H. College of Engg. & Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 23 March 1979, revised 30 May 1983, accepted 3 December 1983

Thiodisuccinic acid, (TDSA), forms stable complexes with cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) of the type $[M_2L.XH_2O]$, $[M=metal; L=ligand; X=6$ for cobalt(II), nickel(II), and 4 for copper(II)] and with chromium(III) of the type $[M_2L.(OH)_2.XH_2O]$ ($X=2$). Their structures have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic moment, electronic and ir spectral studies. Cobalt(II) forms high-spin octahedral complex, nickel(II) and copper(II) form distorted octahedral complexes and chromium(III) forms high-spin typically oxo-bridged octahedral complex. IR spectra show that coordination takes place through carboxylate groups of the ligand and their coordination polyhedron must be completed either by water molecules or -OH bridges or by some intermolecular interactions, probably through free carboxylic oxygens. Relevant ligand field parameters have been calculated for these complexes. The nephelauxetic effect seems to be more effective for cobalt(II) than for nickel(II).

THE complexes of thiocarboxylic acids are interesting because of their enhanced stability and formation of bridged complexes. Some similar compounds have been studied by Jones *et al*¹, Podlaha *et al*²⁻⁵ and Tiwari *et al*⁶⁻⁹. The present communication reports the preparation and characterization of thiodisuccinic acid (TDSA),

$S-\begin{pmatrix} CHCOOH \\ | \\ CH_2COOH \end{pmatrix}_2$ complexes with cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and chromium(III). The acid contains one sulphur atom and four carboxylic groups capable of combining in various polydentate modes.

A noteworthy point here is that sulphur is not coordinated in the complexes, most probably due to steric hindrance caused by the presence of large bulky carboxylic groupings at each end of the molecule and lower affinity of these metals towards sulphur. These result in forcing each end of the molecule to function independently and to chelate different metal atoms.

Experimental

Thiodisuccinic acid (TDSA) (Evans Chemetics, Inc., New York) of 98.1% purity was used without further purification. All other chemicals used were of A. R. grade.

Preparation of the complexes: The metal complexes of thiodisuccinic acid (TDSA) were prepared by refluxing on water bath aqueous solution of corresponding metal chloride [100 ml 0.1 M $CoCl_2$ or $NiCl_2$; 50 ml 0.1 M $CrCl_3$; 100 ml 0.2 M $CuSO_4$] with an equimolar ethanolic solution (50 ml) of TDSA [1 : 1 water ethanol mixture in case of Co(II) only] in presence of a few drops of NaOH solution

to maintain the pH between 5-6. The mixture was heated for 2 hr in case of Co(II) and Ni(II) and concentrated, giving dark red precipitate of Co(II) complex in presence of excess acetone, and green solid for Ni(II) complex. In case of Cu(II) and Cr(III), the mixture was heated for 0.5 hr giving bluish green precipitate of Cu(II) complex and for 1 hr at 80° giving greenish black precipitate of Cr(III) complex. The precipitates so obtained were cooled, filtered and washed with water, ethanol and acetone and finally dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous $CaCl_2$. The complexes of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) were insoluble in common organic solvents but partially soluble in water whereas the Cr(III) complex was insoluble in water as well as common organic solvents.

Physical measurements:

The instruments and methods used were the same as described earlier⁶. The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analysis and decomposition temperatures which range from 220 to 380° show that the complexes are thermally stable.

Cobalt(II) complex: The observed magnetic moment of 4.27 B.M. per Co(II) ion lies well within the range and suggests that the complex is octahedral.

The electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complex (Table 2) consist of two main bands. Although the complex formally have D_{4h} symmetry, the observed spectra can be interpreted in terms of metal ion surrounded by a weak ligand field of micro-symmetry. The lowest energy band at 8.62 kK can

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA*

Complexes and their colour	Decomposition Temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		Carbon	Hydrogen	Sulphur	Metal
[Co ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ S).6H ₂ O] Pinkish	265	20.08 (19.07)	3.81 (3.68)	6.54 (6.56)	24.00 (24.13)
[Ni ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ S).6H ₂ O] Light greenish	260	20.00 (19.68)	3.74 (3.68)	6.40 (6.56)	24.10 (24.13)
[Cu ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ S).4H ₂ O] Bluish green	220	20.90 (20.83)	3.18 (3.04)	6.96 (6.94)	27.48 (27.54)
[Cr ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ S).(OH) ₂ .2H ₂ O] Dark greenish	380	19.68 (19.28)	3.90 (4.01)	6.40 (6.42)	20.86 (20.89)

TABLE 2—DIFFUSE REFLECTANCE SPECTRA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS FOR Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) AND Cr(III) COMPLEXES

Complex	Bands kK	Assignments	Dq cm ⁻¹	Racah parameter B cm ⁻¹	$\frac{\nu_2}{\nu_1}$	β^*	E _{term} ^F separation cm ⁻¹	LFSE kcal/mole	$\frac{972}{1041} \times B_{Ni^{2+}}$
[Co ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ S).6H ₂ O]	8.62	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)(ν_1)	937	954	2.10	0.9815	14310	21.36	972
	10.54	→ ³ E _g							
	18.18	→ ⁴ A _{2g} (F)(ν_2)							
	21.74	→ ⁴ T _{1g} (F)(ν_2)							
	37.70	CT							
	40.90	CT							
[Ni ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ S).6H ₂ O]	8.33	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (F)(ν_1)	833	1045	1.71	1.0000	15675	28.49	—
	12.50								
	13.51	→ ³ T _{1g} (F)(ν_2)							
	14.28								
	15.62	→ ¹ E _g (D)							
	24.39	→ ³ T _{1g} (P)(ν_2)							
	26.38								
	40.00	CT							
[Cu ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ S).4H ₂ O]	13.15	³ E _g → ³ T _{2g}	1315	—	—	—	22.48	—	
	28.58	CT							
	35.71	CT							
	40.00	CT							
[Cr ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ S)(OH) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	14.925	⁴ A _{2g} → ³ E _g	1709	799	1.36	0.776	11990	58.42	—
	17.090	→ ⁴ T _{2g} (F)(ν_1)							
	23.26	→ ⁴ T _{1g} (F)(ν_2)							
	40.00	→ ⁴ T _{1g} (P)(ν_2)							

* B/B₀, where B₀ = Racah parameter for the gaseous ion; Co²⁺ = 972 cm⁻¹, Ni²⁺ = 1041 cm⁻¹; Cr³⁺ = 13800 cm⁻¹.

be assigned as ν_1 and the strong band at 21.74 kK with a shoulder at 18.18 kK as ν_2 transitions. The ligand field parameters (Table 2) have been calculated, using semi-empirical equations⁹, to resolve the problem of assignment of the shoulder.

To solve these equations for Dq and B, experimental values of ν_1 and ν_2 as assigned above have been used. Lever¹⁰ has suggested that the shoulder on the principal band in octahedral cobalt(II) complex for assigning ν_2 transition must have an energy approximately twice but not greater than 2.20 times that of ν_1 transition. This is strictly true for a regular octahedral molecule and well substantiates our calculated value of 2.10 for ν_2/ν_1 which is in good agreement with other complexes of octahedral symmetry⁹. It is, therefore, concluded that the shoulder at 18.18 kK corresponds to ⁴T_{1g} (F) → ⁴A_{2g} transition.

Taking the above values for ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 the ligand field stabilization energy (LFSE) comes to 21.36 kcal/mole. The value of β , 0.9815, indicates

a very low degree of covalency. The spectrum also allows a calculation of the E(⁴P) - E(⁴F), the term separation, 14310 cm⁻¹, corresponding to about 98.68% of the free ion value.

Nickel(II) complex : The present nickel(II) complex was found to be paramagnetic and partially soluble in non-aqueous polar solvents. The observed magnetic moment of 2.16 B.M. per nickel atom (Table 1) is much less than the value expected for high spin octahedral or tetrahedral complexes. A similar magnetic behaviour of Ni(II) complexes with dithioxamide was reported by Kanekar and coworkers¹¹. The low magnetic moment value may be a consequence of a diamagnetic square planar unit contained in the same molecule along with the octahedral unit.

This conclusion is further supported by the electronic spectrum of the complex which shows eight bands (Table 2). For the octahedral species the observed transitions may be ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g} (F) at 8.33 kK (ν_1), ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F) at 14.28 kK (ν_2) and

${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) at 26.38 kK (ν_3). These bands are very similar to those of nickel(II) aquate¹², $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$. In this spectrum the second absorption band corresponding to the transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) is double peaked and is observed at 13.51 and 14.28 kK. It is likely that the octahedral species of the complex is of D_{4h} symmetry. Thus, the observed electronic spectrum can well be interpreted in terms of metal ion surrounded by weak ligand field of microsymmetry. The ligand field splitting energy, 10 Dq, is taken equal to the energy of the first transition (ν_1) and the Racah parameter, B, was calculated from ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 band energies using the diagonal sum rule¹³, $15B = \nu_2 + \nu_3 - 3\nu_1$. This is further confirmed by comparing the separation (X_{obs}) of ν_2 and ν_3 bands, 12.10 kK, with the calculated value (X_{cal}) of 11.28 kK on the basis of octahedral symmetry. The value of ($X_{\text{cal}} - X_{\text{obs}}$), +0.82, is not within the usual limit¹⁴ for undistorted octahedral Ni(II) complex species. Further, for tetragonal Ni(II) complexes, the values of ν_2/ν_1 are found significantly higher than the usual range for octahedral complexes and some times still higher than the theoretical value of 1.80 to 1.50 to 1.70 (Calcd.). Values of about 1.60 to 1.70 are common for Ni(II) complexes of octahedral symmetry. In the present case the ν_2/ν_1 ratio of 1.71 indicates distorted octahedral complex species.

The LFSE comes out to be 28.48 kcal/mole and term separation, $E({}^4P) - E({}^4F)$, of 15675 cm^{-1} corresponds to about 98.96% of the free ion value. The reduction of B after multiplying B ($\frac{\text{Co}^{2+}}{\text{Ni}^{2+}}$) gaseous, the so called nephelauxetic effect¹⁵, seems to be more effective for Co(II) than for Ni(II). The remaining bands at 22.22 and 24.39 kK are the characteristic bands of square planar unit corresponding to ${}^1A_1 \rightarrow {}^1B_1$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. The presence of both distorted octahedral and square planar units accounts well for the observed reduction of magnetic moment. This suggests that the complex contains two nickel atoms of which one is surrounded octahedrally while the other is in a planar environment at the end of the molecule.

Copper(II) complex: The observed magnetic moment of 1.36 B.M. (Table 1) is subnormal in case of Cu(II)-TDSA complex and suggests strong spin-spin coupling between unpaired electrons of neighbouring copper atoms and polymeric structure. The electronic spectrum shows two transition bands at 13.15 and 28.58 kK indicating octahedral symmetry¹⁶. The Cu(II) complex will be distorted octahedral due to Jahn-Teller effect. Therefore, it is suggested that the copper(II) complex is of distorted octahedral structure where the band at 13.15 kK has been ascribed to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition.

Chromium(III) complex: Most of the polymeric chromium(III)-thiodicarboxylate complexes show magnetic moment very close to spin-only value of 3.88 B.M.³⁻⁴ in octahedral stereochemistry. The observed magnetic moment of 3.27 B.M. in the

present case (Table 1) is considerably lower than the one reported above, indicating the presence of spin-orbit coupling within the complex but does not exclude the polymeric structure. This view is further supported specially by the magnetic moment of the chromic complex formed which is typical of an oxobridged polymer, and insolubility of the complex in benzene or chloroform accompanied by marked swelling which is a good evidence for the presence of linear chains as the predominating species¹⁷.

Thermogravimetric analysis of chromium(III) complex shows initial weight loss at 112° corresponding to two water molecules (loss in weight, Calcd. = 8.12% ; Found = 7.8%) as lattice water.

The electronic spectrum of chromium(III) complex (Table 2) shows three spin allowed transitions at 17.09 (ν_1), 23.26 (ν_2) and 40.00 kK (ν_3) corresponding to the transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1), ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_3). The transition at 14.925 kK is just the spin forbidden transition corresponding to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$. It is therefore likely that the complex is of octahedral symmetry. The ligand field splitting energy, 10 Dq, was taken as equal to the first transition (ν_1) and Racah parameter, B, was calculated from ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 band energies¹⁸. The value of ν_2/ν_1 was found to be 2.30 which is greater than 2.20, a value generally accepted for regular octahedral complexes¹⁹. This indicates that the complex has a distorted octahedral microsymmetry. The LFSE calculated comes out to be 58.42 kcal/mole. The spectrum also allows a calculation of the term separation, $E({}^4P) - E({}^4F)$, 11990 cm^{-1} . This corresponds to about 83% of the free ion value.

IR spectra: The infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} . The important bands and their tentative assignments were obtained with reference to the spectra of other carboxylate complexes as well as those of thio and amino acid complexes¹⁹⁻²². The C-S stretching band at 725 cm^{-1} of the ligand on complexation does not shift to lower frequency which clearly indicates uncoordinated sulphur. The antisymmetric stretching band, on complexation, shifted to lower frequencies in the 1550-1635 cm^{-1} region for the Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Cr(III) complexes. These values correspond to those of glycinate and other amino acid complexes. The bridging carboxylic groups of metal carboxylate complexes also show an absorption band in this region. Further, the -OH deformation band at 910 cm^{-1} in the ligand disappears on complexation as the ionization of the carboxylic group is envisaged in coordination. It is, therefore, concluded that coordination takes place through carboxylate groups and the coordination positions are occupied by the bonding and non-bonding oxygen atoms of the carboxylic groups. The position of the band of the antisymmetric COO^- stretching vibrations as well as the difference of the wave numbers of the antisymmetric and symmetric COO^- vibrations, which

are higher than 220 cm^{-1} , indicate the covalent character of the carboxyl metal bond. The observed strong band near 3400 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of water molecules in the complexes. The second observed band at $\sim 930\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was assigned to coordinated water molecules which was further supported by thermogravimetric analysis.

In the chromium(III) complex, a strong band near 990 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $-\text{OH}$ bridging vibrations²³⁻²⁴. This is in accordance with the chemical behaviour typical of an oxo-bridged complex. This suggests that the two OH groups in chromium(III) complex occupy two coordinated positions, thereby making the complex of an octahedral stereochemistry. The infrared spectrum studies support the analysis and electronic spectral findings as stated earlier.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to M/s Chemetics Inc., New York for a gift of thiodisuccinic acid, Prof. W. Rahman, Head, Chemistry Department for facilities and Mr. J. P. Bajpai, Chemistry Department, D. S. College, Aligarh, for valuable suggestions. One of the authors (R. P.) is thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. M. M. JONES, T. H. PRATT and H. C. BROWN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1213.
2. M. M. JONES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 194.
3. J. PODLAHA and J. PODLAHOVA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **4**, 521, 549.
4. J. PODLAHA and J. PODLAHOVA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **5**, 418, 420.
5. J. PODLAHOVA, J. LOUB and C. NOVAK, *Crystallogr.*, 1972, **B28**, 1623.
6. A. KUMAR, S. JAIN and S. K. TIWARI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 2439.
7. S. K. TIWARI, A. KUMAR, S. JAIN and N. P. PARASHAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 872.
8. S. K. TIWARI, R. PRAKASH and D. P. S. RATHORE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 537.
9. J. REEDIZK, W. L. DRIESSEN and W. I. GROENEVELD, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1969, **88**, 1095.
10. A. B. P. LEVER, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1967, 2041.
11. C. R. KANEKAR and A. T. CASEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3105.
12. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 1362.
13. O. BOSTRUPP and C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chim. Scand.*, 1957, **11**, 1223.
14. A. B. P. LEVER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, **3**, 119.
15. A. D. LIEHR, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 1314.
16. J. P. FACKLER, JR., F. A. COTTON and D. W. BARNUM, *Inorg. Chem. Educ.*, 1963, **2**, 97.
17. T. G. DUNNE, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1967, **44**, 101.
18. "Introduction to Ligand Fields", (Ed.) B. N. FIGGIS, Interscience Publisher, New York, 1970, p. 232.
19. C. A. MCAULIFFE and W. D. PHERRY, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1969, 634.
20. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1963, pp. 197-225.
21. C. G. BARRALLOUGH, R. L. MARTIN and I. M. STEWART, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, **22**, 891.
22. S. E. WIBERLEY, S. C. BUNCE and W. H. BANNER, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1961, **32**, 217.
23. N. NAKAMOTO, J. FUJITA and M. MOBAYASHI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **79**, 3295, 3963.
24. S. K. TIWARI, S. JAIN and A. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 310.